

Towards an ontology for co-simulation scenarios of energy systems

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1 Introduction

The global transition towards sustainable energy systems requires innovative solutions to integrate diverse energy technologies and systems efficiently. Co-simulation has emerged as an important approach to address this challenge, enabling the analysis of interconnected energy systems by coupling different domain-specific simulation models. It facilitates a comprehensive understanding of the interactions between various components, such as renewable generation, energy storage, loads, and grid infrastructure, under complex and dynamic scenarios, while being more flexible than a monolithic approach to simulation and allowing to reuse existing simulation models.

However, the effective use of co-simulation is often hindered by the lack of a standardized framework for defining and managing scenarios across different simulation domains. A consistent and interoperable representation of scenarios is crucial for ensuring reproducibility, comparability, facilitating collaboration, and enabling automated workflows in co-simulation studies. In this context, a scenario ontology is a promising solution. By applying ontology-based approaches, it becomes possible to standardize scenario definitions semantically and enhance interoperability. Furthermore, the integration of simulation models into scenarios can be transformed into a computer-assisted process based on a registry. This registry serves as a structured catalog of simulation models and enables automated discovery, compatibility checks, and seamless integration of simulation models into scenarios. This effort aims to significantly reduce the manual effort and time required to align simulation models with the specific requirements of scenarios while ensuring consistency and accuracy.

Additionally, a scenario ontology can serve as the foundation for hosting co-simulation in a Software-as-a-Service architecture that we will reference as Simulation-as-a-Service (SimaaS) in the following, which requires precise and flexible configuration files to deploy simulations in cloud-based environments. It allows users to access, configure, and execute simulations without managing the underlying computational infrastructure. The SimaaS approach aims to enhance scalability, and facilitate the sharing and reuse of scenarios.

This paper presents the development of a scenario ontology tailored for co-simulation of energy systems. It aims to be compatible with different co-simulation frameworks and will be exemplarily implemented in the NFDI4Energy consortium for the frameworks mosaik [1], DaceDS [2], and VILLASframework [3].

2 State of the art

An overview of existing ontologies in context of energy system research was already provided in [4], and in [5] simulation ontologies were evaluated based on their representation of simulation scenarios. The energy-focused ontologies can be relevant for the semantic description of simulation components, but the ontologies in the overviews lack representation of simulation scenarios as described in the introduction. Therefore, only a few described aspects are relevant for a scenario ontology and might be reused.

A process for an assisted creation process of co-simulation scenarios is described in [6], which uses a catalog of simulation models and metadata description of the content. Also the Open Energy Platform (OEP), provides several services aiming to support creation and reuse of artifacts in energy system research. For example, it provides a database with model factsheets to describe different simulation models [7], [8].

Many different co-simulation frameworks exist in the energy research domain. As mentioned, for our work the three frameworks mosaik, DaceDS, and VILLASframework will be exemplarily integrated as they represent different types of co-simulation. Mosaik represents an established software co-simulation framework with focus on user-friendly flexible scenario creation [1], [9]. DaceDS uses a publish-subscribe-middleware approach and was originally developed for the traffic domain, but is adapted to energy system simulation [2]. VILLASframework enables distributed real-time co-simulation with integration of hardware devices [3].

3 Approach

For the ontology development we follow the Linked Open Terms (LOT) approach [10]. Based on that, we started with defining use cases¹ and requirements in form of competency questions. For the next step – ontology conceptualization – we looked specifically in the scenario definition of the three frameworks mosaik, DaceDS, and VILLASframework, but also into the literature and existing simulation ontologies [5]. We collected crucial terms for the technical definition of scenarios and started to discuss their meaning and how they relate to existing definitions, e.g., in other ontologies.

The concept of a scenario can be used quite differently and applies differing terminologies when having a detailed look at frameworks. Therefore, we plan to define a general simulation scenario ontology, which contains the general concepts and can be extended with additional modules for the specific frameworks. Thus, different frameworks can be aligned with the general scenario structure to improve interoperability, but specific details needed for execution can be modeled in more detail for each framework. Full interoperability can not be achieved in that way as the frameworks are too diverse, but it can help for the development of a common usable tool set for finding simulation components and building as well as comparing scenarios.

Beyond the general technical definition of scenarios, also domain-specific aspects have to be considered. For simulation of energy systems usually a grid topology is

¹https://github.com/NFDI4Energy/simulation-service-requirements/blob/main/use_cases.md

needed, which is a crucial part of the scenario definition, because additional simulation models are usually mapped to it. Thus, the specification of a grid topology has to be also part of the scenario ontology and the integration of a suitable standard, like for example the Common Information Model (CIM) [11], is planned.

Also the goal of the scenario has to be modeled [12], to enable support in finding suitable simulation models to create meaningful scenarios and evaluate specific results. For this, also input and output data has to be semantically defined based on a domain ontology, that will be developed separately in NFDI4Energy as described in [4]. This domain ontology will be based on the Open Energy Ontology (OEO) [13] because it was identified as the most relevant ontology in the energy research domain [4]. Thus, we plan to make the scenario ontology part of the OEO or at least a compatible extension to it.

4 Conclusion

This paper presents the concept for a scenario ontology for co-simulation of energy systems offering standardized scenario definitions. The main contributions are to (1) allow a specification of co-simulation scenarios to improve interoperability between different frameworks, enable reproducible workflows, and foster comparison of scenarios; (2) support a registry-based approach for finding simulation models suitable for the simulation goals; (3) facilitate SimaaS approaches based on the scenario specification.

The conceptualization of the scenario ontology is currently ongoing and a first version of the ontology is planned to be published in the year 2025. At the NFDI4Energy conference, we will present the following to get feedback and potentially adapt the development:

- The general approach as described in this paper
- Up-to-date state of the ontology conceptualization and development
- Overview of used or integrated external ontologies and plans for the future
- Plans for integration of ontology into the NFDI4Energy simulation services

The benefits of the new processes will be shown in task area 6 of NFDI4Energy. It includes two use cases for the presented co-simulation ontology. This first use case will demonstrate how to semantically describe an electromagnetic transient (EMT) co-simulation with various heterogeneous components including a hardware in the loop load component. The components will be coupled using the VILLASnode framework and it shall also demonstrate the automated execution from a single entry point - explicitly starting the components remotely and transferring the necessary simulation models accordingly to perform the simulation. The second use case will demonstrate a distributed agent-based simulation of flexibility options on low-voltage level grid based on the co-simulation frameworks mosaik and DaceDS.

Data availability statement

Use cases and requirements for the scenario ontology and the whole simulation service task area of NFDI4Energy will be published in a GitHub repository ².

The described ontology will be published in a GitHub repository ³.

²<https://github.com/NFDI4Energy/simulation-service-requirements>

³<https://github.com/NFDI4Energy/simulation-scenario-ontology>

Underlying and related material

Not applicable.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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